

Adsorption dynamics – temperature effect on adsorption of lead(II) species onto lignite surface

N. Balasubramanian^{a*} and A. Jafar Ahamed^b

^aP. G. and Research Department of Chemistry, Bishop Heber College, Tiruchirappalli-620 017, India

^bP. G. and Research Department of Chemistry, Jamal Mohamed College, Tiruchirappalli-620 020, India

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Among the various techniques, adsorption process is found suitable for the removal of lead(II) species from wastewater. The effect of temperature on the adsorption characteristics of lead(II) by lignite is discussed. The various models, such as Lagergren and Weber-Morris are tested and the results are interpreted.

In continuation of our studies on lignite¹, the present investigation describes the mechanism of adsorption of lead(II) species onto the outer surface of lignite. The study involves removal of lead from a wastewater by adsorption technique using this cheaply available adsorbent material.

Results and Discussion

pH of wastewater is considered a significant controlling factor for any adsorption process². In order to minimise hydrolysis of $\text{Pb}^{\text{II}}(\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2)$ at higher pH values of the medium (viz. >4.0)³, experiments were conducted in the pH range 1–4. Adsorption experiments were conducted using a lead nitrate solution of concentration around 500 mg dm^{-3} and a lignite suspension of concentration around 4.0 g dm^{-3} (particle size $0\text{--}63 \mu$, dried at 105°) and at pH values 1.40, 1.88, 2.37, 3.62, 3.83 and 3.96. The results indicate that maximum lead removal occurs in pH around 3.62.

Adsorption data for the removal of lead by lignite under a given set of operating conditions are presented graphically in Fig. 1. The equilibrium time is found to be 240 min and the amount of lead removed at equilibrium is 37.4%. In order to obtain information about the influence of temperature on adsorption characteristics, experiments were carried out at five different temperatures, viz. 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50° , keeping all other conditions constant. Fig. 1 shows the influence of contact time on lead removal at different temperatures. The equilibrium time decreases with the increase in temperature. The times of attainment of equilibrium at temperatures 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50° under the same operating conditions are 240, 150, 130, 120 and 110 min respectively. The amount of lead removed also decreases from 37.4 to 13.0% with the increase in temperature from 30 to 50° . A similar finding was observed⁴ in the study of chromium removal, though reverse trends are not unusual⁵. The results suggest that the adsorption process is exothermic. With the increase in temperature, the escaping

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time on lead removal at different temperatures : (o) 30° , (\square) 35° , (Δ) 40° , (\bullet) 45° and (\blacksquare) 50° ; $[\text{Pb}^{\text{II}}]_{\text{ini}} = \sim 500.0 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$, $W_{\text{adsorbent}} = \sim 4.0 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$, $\text{size}_{\text{adsorbent}} = 0\text{--}63 \mu$, solution pH = 3.62.

tendency of lead from the interface increases and thereby favour the desorption process which leads to the declining trend.

An attempt has been made to analyse the results (Table 1) in the light of the Lagergren model with a view to evaluating the mechanistic parameters associated with the adsorption process. The Lagergren equation is

$$\log_{10}(q_e - q) = -\frac{k_{\text{Lager}}}{2.303} t + \log_{10} q_e \quad (1)$$

where, q is the amount of metal ion adsorbed per unit

weight of the adsorbent and q_e that at equilibrium, k_{Lager} is the Lagergren rate constant and t the time. This equation suggests linearity for the plot of $\log_{10}(q_e - q)$ against time and the relation is shown in Fig. 2. The plot is biphasic and this may be due to different factors, such as change in the

Fig. 2. Lagergren plot : $[Pb^{II}]_{ini} = 502.8 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$, $W_{adsorbent} = 4.04 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$, $size_{adsorbent} = 0-63 \mu$, solution pH = 3.62, temp. = 30° , $q_e = 46.53 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$.

number of active sites and change in the mode of adsorption. The analysis of this figure shows a very rapid rate during the initial period. A slower rate was observed in the period 30–160 min. This was followed again by a faster rate during the period 160–200 min. The rapid rate observed in the initial period, may be attributed to the availability of a large number of uncovered active sites on the surface of the adsorbent.

From the slope of each line, the rate constant was calculated. The values ($k_{Lager} \times 10^4, \text{ s}^{-1}$) for Phase I and Phase II are found to be 2.02 and 4.50 respectively. From these values, the values of half-life for adsorption were determined and these are found to be 3.43×10^3 and 1.54×10^3 s respectively. The applicability of the Lagergren model to the present system suggests the formation of a molecular layer of lead species onto the surface of the adsorbent and the process follows first order kinetics^{4,6}.

It is of interest to study the possibility of the adsorbate species to diffuse into the interior sites of the particles of adsorbent. For this purpose, Weber-Morris equation was tested,

$$q = \frac{x}{m} = k_{id} t^{0.5} \quad (2)$$

where, q is the amount of metal ion adsorbed per unit weight of the adsorbent, x the amount adsorbed, m the

weight of the adsorbent, k_{id} the rate constant for intraparticle diffusion and $t^{0.5}$ the time.

Fig. 3(a) depicts the plots of x/m against $t^{0.5}$. The plot shows a curved portion and a linear portion. The initial

Fig. 3. Weber and Morris plot : (a) $[Pb^{II}]_{ini} = 502.8 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$, $W_{adsorbent} = 4.04 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$, $size_{adsorbent} = 0-63 \mu$, temp. = 30° , solution pH = 3.62; (b) $[Pb^{II}]_{ini} = 500.0 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$, $W_{adsorbent} = 4.0 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$, $size_{adsorbent} = 0-63 \mu$, temp. = 45° , solution pH = 3.62.

curved portion (Phase I) indicates the removal of about 22% of lead within $5.5 \text{ min}^{0.5}$. It manifests an average rate of removal of $26.7 \text{ mg g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-0.5}$. The curved portion represents boundary layer adsorption. The linear portion (Phase II) represents slow diffusion of the adsorbate species from the surface film into the micropores⁷. From the slope of the linear portion, the rate parameter (k_{id}) was determined. The Lagergren rate constants determined at different temperatures, viz. 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50° are found to be 2.02, 2.17, 3.11, 4.75 and 5.76 respectively, while the respective amount of lead removed are 37.4, 20.2, 19.4, 19.0 and 13.1%. The results show an increasing trend in rate constant and decreasing trend in the amount removed with the increase in temperature. Thus low temperature favours adsorption. This kind of temperature effect indicates the exothermic nature of the adsorption process.

The values of k_{id} determined at 30, 40 and 45° are found to be 2.24, 2.49 and $2.62 \text{ mg g}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-0.5}$ respectively. The overall rate constants ($k_{Lager} \times 10^4, \text{ s}^{-1}$) at 30 and 45° are 2.02 and 4.75 respectively, indicating that with the increase in temperature from 30 to 45° , the overall rate constant is roughly doubled. On the other hand, with the increase in temperature from 30 to 45° , the increase in k_{id} is very small, which shows that the influence of temperature on k_{id} is not considerable. This may probably be accounted for by suggesting that the simultaneous increase in the rate of adsorption and that of desorption leads to insignificant change in the value of k_{id} with the increase in temperature. In order to justify these results, some more data are required by some other means too.

For this purpose, the value of D_p at different temperature were determined,

$$D_p = \frac{0.030 \gamma_0^2}{t_{1/2}} \quad (3)$$

where, D_p is the pore diffusion coefficient ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), r_0 the radius of the particle of the adsorbent (cm) and $t_{1/2}$ the time for half of adsorption(s). The results reveal that D_p varies from 2.17×10^{-11} to $6.19 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ when the temperature is increased from 30 to 50°. The D_p value in the range 10^{-11} to $10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ indicates that the rate-controlling step involves pore diffusion⁹. Thus, the present results may be corroborative to the fact that increase in temperature increases pore diffusion.

Table 1. Data for Lagergren plot

$[\text{Pb}^{II}]_{\text{ini}} = 502.8 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$, $W_{\text{adsorbent}} = 4.04 \text{ g dm}^{-3}$,
 $\text{size}_{\text{adsorbent}} = 0-63 \mu$, solution pH = 3.62, temp. = 30°, $q_e = 46.53 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$

Contact time t , min	$[\text{Pb}^{II}]_{\text{adsorbed}}$, x , mg dm^{-3}	$(x/m), q$, mg g^{-1}	$(q_e - q)$, mg g^{-1}	$10 + \log_{10}(q_e - q)$
30	107.9	26.71	19.80	11.297
60	130.4	32.28	14.22	11.153
90	146.3	36.21	10.28	11.013
120	158.7	39.28	7.21	10.857
150	169.4	41.93	4.6	10.663
180	178.6	44.21	2.3	10.362
210	184.4	45.64	0.8	9.903
240	188.0	46.53	0	0

Although the values of k_{id} do not indicate much on the variation of the influence of temperature on pore diffusion, the values of x -intercept in the Weber-Morris plot will be useful. The Weber-Morris plot at 45° is shown in Fig. 3(b). The x -intercept lies at around $1.7 \text{ min}^{0.5}$. However, the x -intercept at 30° (Fig. 3(a)) is close to zero. These findings indicate that the boundary layer adsorption contributes largely to the rate-determining step with the increase in temperature of the solution. This may be attributed to the fact that boundary layer thickness decreases with the increase in temperature, causing increase in the boundary layer adsorption. This type of decrease in the thickness of the boundary layer and subsequent increase in the boundary layer adsorption with the increase in temperature account for the exothermic nature of the present adsorbate-adsorbent system.

Experimental

Lignite was collected from Neyveli Lignite Corporation

Limited, Neyveli, India. The powdered material was sieved (63μ) and retained in a zero number sieve. It was dried overnight at 105° and used after cooling.

Measurement of solution pH : Lead nitrate solution of known concentration was adjusted to a known pH value. A known volume of the solution was mixed with a known amount of the adsorbent. Immediately after separating the adsorbent, the pH of the clear solution was measured and it was reported as the solution pH. It is to be noted that the pH of the solution varied after mixing the adsorbent with the adsorbate solution. The extent of variation depends on the initial pH. However, in the pH range studied, variation was found very little. In addition, at the end of equilibrium, pH was measured. The difference was found negligible.

Study of adsorption kinetics : Batch-mode adsorption study was conducted. An accurately weighed amount of lignite was mixed with a known volume of lead nitrate solution of known concentration and pH. It was kept shaken mechanically in a temperature-controlled mechanical water-bath shaker. After a definite interval of time, the adsorbent was separated and the clear solution was analysed, after filtration, for the residual lead content. Lead was estimated by titrimetric method.

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